

Ethnic history of West (Ancient) Asia, South and Southeast Asia, Central and East Asia

Ethnogenesis and ethnic history, language and race, economic and social system, material and spiritual culture

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Abstract: Each discipline differs from other disciplines by its research subject and methods. Ethnology has been studying the ethnic structure of peoples and the culture formed along with it since its emergence as a science. At the same time, the formation of any field of science as a science is closely related to the needs of people. In this article, we will see how important science is in the study of the ethnology of Asian peoples. In this article, we will get acquainted with the geographical division of Asian peoples and their ethnology. The population of each region is briefly described in the article.

According to the current scientific development in the science of history, the history of the origin of each nation consists of two stages. The first stage is ethnogenesis, the second stage is ethnic history. The ethnogenesis part of a nation's history includes the period before its formation as a people, a nation. Folk ethnogenesis is a very long historical and ethnocultural process. Its genesis begins with the union of tribe and tribe. When the ethnogenesis of the nation under study is completed, its ethnic history begins. Ethnic history is also a long-lasting historical and ethnocultural process, and when ethnic history reaches a certain point in its development, the process of its formation as a nation begins. Ethnogenesis and ethnic history of peoples are studied based on this scientific-methodological basis ^[1]. The constant increase in the number of

people worldwide, the complexity of production relations, and cultural development are the reason for the constant increase in mass migration, the mixing of different peoples. Due to a certain dependence on nature in the early stages of human history, the world's population increased very slowly over thousands of years. In ancient times and in the Middle Ages, despite high birth rates, constant disease, epidemics, wars, and increased death rates resulted. That's why the birth rate was higher than the death rate in the world at this time. A thousand years ago, the transition of the people living in the Middle East to a sedentary lifestyle and the wide spread of agriculture and animal husbandry reduced people's dependence on nature and caused their population to grow. As a result of these innovations, 4-5 thousand years ago, the population of the Earth increased by approximately 25 million people. During this period, the main population of our motherland lived in Ancient Egypt, Mesopotamia, India, between the Huanghe and Yangtze rivers, and in Central Asia. The subsequent ethnic history of humanity was closely connected with the process of improvement of economic relations. As a result of these factors, the number of people on earth has increased significantly. According to approximate estimates of anthropologists and ethnologists, the world population reached 150-200 million people at the beginning of the Middle Ages, that is, two thousand years ago. According to archaeologists and paleontologists, 70% of the main population lived in Asia during this period ^[2]. The number of these indicators is increasing year by year. People living in Asia still make up 70 percent of the world's population. Their ethnic process to this day is also related to the number of peoples living there.

The first centers of civilization arose in ancient times in Asia. Great states (Babylon, Sumer, Assyria, Harappa, Urartu, etc.) and kingdoms (Baburids, Ottomans) arose and disintegrated here for centuries. In the 19th century, several countries in Asia were colonies of Europeans. In the 20th century, great changes took place in the political map of Asia. As a result of the national liberation struggle, Mongolia (1921), Vietnam (1945), Korea (1948), as well as former colonies of the United Kingdom gained independence (India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Jordan, Maldives, Malaysia, Singapore, Yemen, Indonesia, Syria, Lebanon, Laos, Cambodia). The State of Israel and the Palestinian Authority emerged in a part of Palestine. In 1971, the state of the United Arab Emirates was formed from the union of the emirates of Abu Dhabi, Dubai, Sharjah, Al Fujairah, Umm al-Qaywain, and Ajman. In 1991, due to the disintegration of the Russian Empire, Uzbekistan, Turkmenistan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and

Kazakhstan gained independence in Central Asia. More than 1/4 of the territory of Asia, its northern part is part of the Russian Federation. In 2000, the state of East Timor was established [3].

Currently, Asia is one of the fastest growing regions. According to the classification adopted by the UN; Asia is divided into 5 subregions:

1. East Asia. China, South and North Korea, Mongolia, Japan.
2. Western Asia. Azerbaijan, Armenia, Georgia, Bahrain, Israel, Jordan, Iraq, Iran, Yemen, Qatar, Cyprus, Kuwait, Lebanon, UAE, Oman, Palestine, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Turkey.
3. Southeast Asia. Brunei, East Timor, Vietnam, Indonesia, Cambodia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Singapore, Thailand, Philippines, Timor, Vietnam, Indonesia, Cambodia, Laos, Malaysia, Myanmar, Singapore, Thailand, Philippines.
4. South Asia. Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, India, Maldives, Nepal, Pakistan, Sri Lanka.
5. Central Asia. Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan [4].

Western Asia (Ancient Asia) is the conventional name for the regions located in the western and southwestern parts of the Asian continent. Western Asia naturally includes Asia Minor, Arabia, the Sinai Peninsula and adjacent areas (Cyprus, the Caucasus, most of the Eastern Taurus Mountains, the Mesopotamian lowlands and Areas on the eastern coast of the Mediterranean Sea, in particular the Levant lands) are included. The area is 7.5 million km² [5]. The climate is characteristic of the regions adjacent to the Mediterranean Sea, while the Mediterranean climate is subtropical continental in the southeast. Turkey (86 million 2024 census), Iran (79.1 million, 2016), Afghanistan (32.2 million, 2019), Iraq (37 million, 2015), Saudi Arabia (34.2 million, 2019), Yemen (20.7 million in 2002), Syria (18.4 million in 2002) lead the region. It is known that religion plays a very important role in the life of society. The economic development of the state and the level of education of the population are of great importance in this. Knowing the religious composition of the population and correctly assessing it allows for a correct understanding and understanding of most of the events and phenomena taking place in the world. At the same time, if we look at the scale of the continents, all major religions and major national religions are widespread in Asia. In Asia, especially, Islam plays a big role. The Sunni branch of Islam occupies the main place in all the Arab countries of Western Asia and partially in Turkey, Yemen and Iraq. Anthropologically, the peoples of West Asia

mainly belong to the European race. Their characteristic features are black hair and eyes, wheatish skin color, medium nose, small and slightly thick lips. Some of the Old Asian or Armanoid type are distinguished by the size of the skull and nose. The Mediterranean type or Indo-Pamir type is distinguished by such distinguishing features as a soft face and a thin lip and a small nose. Some ethnic groups have a partially mongoloid, some groups have a negroid type, and the austrolopoid type is shown in the Afghan and Iranian burghs. Not one of the current languages of the population of West Asia is included in the local indigenous languages Sumerian is known from history Sumerian, Semitic, Kassite, Lulebai, Caspian, Caucasian languages are Kava, Hurrian and Urartian languages. The appearance of the Semitic or Semitic languages corresponds to the end of the 4th and the beginning of the 3rd millennium BC. And in the 1st millennium, it mixes with languages that came from North Africa. In addition to the local state languages, until the Arab conquest and the spread of Islam in the region (7th century), the Aramaic language was considered the common language in the region and even in Central Asia. After the spread of Islam, the Arabic language and later the Turkish tribes that appeared in the ethnic structure of this region caused the formation of the local language of each region. The spread and emergence of these languages is directly related to the ethnogenesis and ethnic history of peoples. As we said above, Asia was the cradle of world civilization. The oldest culture was created here. Ancient Asian artistic and historical monuments are as wide and colorful as Egyptian art. Luxurious palaces and temples were built here. In round sculpture and relief, wonderful medium-dynamic, plastic beautiful works were created, mural paintings, delicate practical and decorative items were used. But these monuments have not reached us. The reason for this is the continuous battle for the domination of the country between the two new states that replaced each other in the two river basins (Mesopotamia), which formed the main part of Ancient Asia, secondly, it can be said that there was not enough stone, wood and metals to develop the types of architecture and visual arts. Preserved monuments and their remains testify to the emergence and development of a unique art in Ancient Asia as early as 4000-3000 BC. Writing was the first to appear here, types of architecture were created, and handicrafts flourished here.

The Indochina Peninsula in the southeastern part of the Eurasian continent and the islands of the Malayan archipelago are inhabited by various peoples with their own culture. Sometimes Southeast Asia is also included in South Asia^[6]. The language group spoken in this

area includes the (Chinese) Tibetan language family belonging to the Indo-European language family. This language is spoken by 23% of the world's population. In addition, the Davidic family includes people living in southern India and eastern Sri Lanka. The population living in this area belongs to the Mongoloid (Asian horn) race. In ancient times, there were more Mon-Khmer-speaking tribes in the Indo-Chinese peninsula. In Indonesia and the Philippine Islands there are Negro-Austroloid peoples mixed with Papuan and Melanesian types. At the beginning of our era, the Mongoloid peoples, who began to come from the north and east, drove out the Mon-Khmer and founded the modern languages of Viet, Thai, Lao and Burmese. In the 7th-8th and especially in the 14th centuries, Islam began to spread to Indonesia and Malaysia, partially to the Philippines, Vietnam and Cambodia. The fertile soil, humid and hot climate of South-East Asia has caused the spread of agriculture, especially rice, since ancient times. As mentioned above, rice cultivation appeared here in the Neolithic period, and it was first occupied by the Thai and Austronesian peoples. Now plow farming is the main occupation of the people of Southeast Asia, where they harvest twice a year in many places. Apart from rice, they grow legumes and root crops, maize, horticulture and vegetables. Among technical crops, rubber and coffee trees, coconut palms are also planted. The tools of production are almost the same: they cultivate the land with a simple wooden plow and a toothed trowel, they dig the plowed land with wood and sow seeds, or they thresh it by sending finished goods. Among the main crops, for example, in Vietnam, rice, paddy, corn, rubber tree, root crops, tea and cotton are grown. In Laos, red smooth rice, horticulture, vegetable growing, partly animal husbandry and fishing have developed. Craftsmanship is still widespread today. In Vietnam, crafts such as the production of various tools, household items, gauze, art products, lacquer and jewelry, weaving tickets, fans, and hats have been popular since ancient times. In Laos and Thailand, cotton and silk gauze, ticket products are woven. In Burma and Kampuchea, lacquer, jewelry and metalwork, and artistic sculpture are highly developed. Batik, a special national fabric, is woven with great skill only in Java, and carving is famous in Bali. Currently, many tools and household items are traditionally produced at home in the agricultural holdings.

The ethnogenesis and ethnic history of East Asians is extremely rich and complex. The origin is also different. It is assumed that the ancestors of the Chinese people lived along the banks of the Huanghe River. The anthropological, historical-archaeological researches and ethnolinguistic data conducted in recent years allow us to have a general idea of the history of

the formation of the peoples of East Asia. In 10 thousand years BC, several Neolithic cultural centers appeared in East Asia. The Xinliangan culture, discovered on the eastern coast of present-day China, laid the groundwork for the emergence of the so-called "eastern" ethnic groups. At that time, the famous Yangshao Neolithic farming culture appeared in the Weixue Valley, the main tributary of the Huanghe River, which formed the basis of the most ancient ancestors of the Chinese people, and a part of it caused the formation of the Tibeto-Burmese ethnoses. The people of Yangshao lived on the banks of the river and in small houses built on stilts those engaged in crafts. Thus, at the beginning of the 1st millennium BC, the formation process of the ancient Chinese ethnoses, which lasted for a long time in the plains of Central China, ended, and they began to call themselves "Huaxia". The emergence of the ethnic unity of the ancient Chinese was the initial impetus for the unification of the states in the basins of the Huanghe and Yangtze rivers in those times. Among the oldest economic and cultural types, groups of hunters, fishermen and gatherers appeared in the Mesolithic period and were not preserved in a pure state. Forest gatherers and hunters found in the warm climate zone were partially preserved in the Mon-Khmer peoples of China. In the north-eastern regions, till recent times, peoples of harvesters and fishermen of temperate climate lived. The ethnogenesis of the Japanese people has not yet been fully determined. As mentioned above, Japanese is not an independent language. The Japanese islands were previously uninhabited. The earliest culture of the Japanese, known collectively as "Jomon" dating back to the Neolithic period, mixed with alien populations - the Ainu from the Indonesian islands and Koreans from China - to create a complex ethnic group. In the 1st century in Japan, the clan system of the clan gradually disintegrated, classes appeared, and in the 7th century a single state was established. At that time, Chinese influence was great, and its writing and cultural elements were passed on. It's true. The formation of the Japanese and Korean peoples as an independent nation dates back to the VII-XII centuries.

The ancestors of the Koreans are located in the 11th millennium BC. They came from southern Manchuria and northern China by land and by sea. The Mongols appeared much later. Their ancestors, the Xiongnu, established the Xiongnu Empire in Central Asia between the 1st and 11th thousand years of our era, which included present-day Mongolia and Northern China. The Huns and Xianbei tribes, who lived in the 1st millennium BC, also took part in the ethnogenesis of the Mongols. In the 12th century, large Mongolian tribal alliances such as Tatars, Naimans, and Merkits appeared in the deserts of Mongolia. In the 13th century, these peoples and tribes united

under the leadership of Temuchin (Genghis Khan) and founded the Mongolian nation. He was freed as a result of heroic struggle in the 17th century.

The peoples of Central Asia were called by different names in different historical periods. Ancient Central Asia included not only the present-day Central Asian territories, but also the north-eastern parts of Iran and the northern parts of Afghanistan. The kingdom of Iran in these areas in the 6th century BC. In the 4th century, Alexander the Great ruled the Greek-Macedonian kingdom. In the centuries before Christ, these territories were part of the Khorezm and Kang states, and later the Kushan kingdom, the Turkish khanate, and the Arab caliphate. In the 10th-11th centuries, the Sani, Seljuk, and Ghaznavid states emerged in ancient Central Asia. To a certain extent, these territories also came under the rule of the Karakhanids. At the end of the 12th century - the beginning of the 13th century, it was under the control of the Kingdom of Khorezm. From the end of the second decade of the 13th century, these territories were occupied by the Mongol invaders. In the 70s of the XIV century, the state of Amir Temur was established. From the end of the XV century to the beginning of the XVI century, these lands were dependent on the Shaybani and then the Ashtarkhani states. Finally, in the middle of the 18th century, three khanates, the Bukhara Emirate, the Khiva Khanate and the Kokan Khanate, were formed. In the second half of the 19th century, ARA Turkestan became a colony of the Russian Empire. Kokan khanate will be abolished soon. The country will be turned into a raw material base of Russia. Thus, the lands of Central Asia were under the care and oppression of foreign countries for almost 26 centuries. According to written sources, from the end of the 16th century to the beginning of the 17th century until 1924, these lands were called Turkestan. The population of Central Asia is divided into several groups in terms of languages. Many people speak languages and dialects belonging to the Turkic language group of the Altai family. This group includes Uzbek, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Karakalpak, Turkmen, Uyghur, and Tatar languages. The Turkic-speaking population makes up more than 60 percent of the peoples of the entire region. There is also a larger population belonging to the Iranian group, which speaks languages belonging to the Indo-European family. Russians, Ukrainians, Belarusians, Dungons, Koreans, or Yaly, local Gypsies and Arabs living in the region are also descendants of peoples belonging to several linguistic groups. Therefore, Central Asia is considered a multi-ethnic region, where hundreds of nations and peoples live together. In addition to the Tajiks, there are Yagnobs, Shugnans, Rushans, Wakhans, Bartangs, Yozhguloms, Ishkamish, Bajyuys and a number of other Pamir and

pre-Pamir peoples. Along with local Uzbeks, Tajiks, Kyrgyz, Kazakhs, Karakalpaks and Turkmens, many peoples who arrived in different historical periods live in the Central Asian region. Many ethnic groups such as Arabs, Jews, Uighurs, Dungans, Tatars, Koreans and Gypsies can be included among these peoples. The route of the Great Silk Road in the region and Islam, which spread after the Arab conquest in the 7th century, leave terrace. The introduction of spices from India along the Great Silk Road caused a special smell and taste in food, and the introduction of tea from China made tea, along with water, a special place on the table. Pork is not consumed in the region at all. This is also considered as one of the main signs and characteristics of the region.

In conclusion, it is worth saying that the cultural diversity of modern nations is increasing, and each nation is trying to preserve its unique cultural characteristics. Social and cultural changes have always been an important part of human evolution We also witnessed this in the brief statement about the geographical regions of Asia that we got acquainted with above. Usually, a person can live from one social group to another, from one country to another during his life, but in any case he does not give up his ethnic affiliation. And this, in turn, forces him to perceive in his own way and conduct life activities based on a certain normative measure. Therefore, the manifestations of culture may not only be specific to a certain ethnic group, but also apply to several ethnic groups.

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